

Effect of Purple Onion (*Allium Cepa*) Extract on Serum Electrolytes, Liver Function Parameters and Haematological Indices of Paracetamol-Induced Oxidative Stress in Wistar Rats

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Abstract-: Purple onion (*Allium cepa*) is one of the most important condiment plants grown and consumed all over the world for its nutritional and pharmacological effects. It has antioxidant potentials due to the presence of high amounts of organosulfur compounds, polyphenols and flavonoids. This study investigated the effect of purple onion (*Allium cepa*) extract on the weight, serum electrolytes, liver function parameters and haematological indices associated with oxidative stress induced by paracetamol in albino Wistar rats. Completely randomized block design (CRBD) was used for this study. The animals were randomly grouped into six (6) groups, with five (5) animals in each group. Group 1 (normal control) was administered normal saline; group 2 (negative control) were induced with oxidative stress using paracetamol without treatment with the purple onion extract. Groups 3, 4 and 5 (treatment groups 1, 2 and 3) were treated with 125mg/kg, 250mg/kg and 500mg/kg of the extract respectively, while group 6 (positive control) were administered 1ml of 100mg/dL of the extract. After twenty-eight days blood samples were collected via cardiac puncture and analyzed. The Mg, K and Ca content of the samples were determined using the method reported by Kabiru et al. (2016). Cl and Na content of the samples were determined using the method reported by Skeggs and Hochstrasser, (1964). Bicarbonate content of the samples were determined using the method reported by Roger et al. (1976). The liver function tests and albumin content of the samples were conducted using the method reported by Limdi and Hyde (2003). Total protein content of the samples was determined using Biuret method. Haematological parameters of the samples were determined according to the method reported by Cheesbrough, (2000). The results revealed that animals in all the study groups except for the positive control group gained weight. The extract was able to maintain electrolyte homeostasis in the experimental subjects without reversing the oxidative stress. High dosage of the extract elevated albumin and total protein levels. Haematological indices, including red blood cell count, hemoglobin and packed cell volume showed no significant differences ($p>0.05$) between the groups. The extract demonstrated significant hepatoprotective effects. Hence, it is recommended for consideration as a traditional medicine for the management of liver injuries due to oxidative stress. This underscores the need for further studies in this regard in order to optimize dosages for therapeutic efficacy and establish safety guidelines.

Keywords: Allium cepa extract, oxidative stress, serum electrolytes, hepatoprotective, haematological.

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1.0 Introduction

Allium cepa L. (purple onion) is a culinary and medicinal herb belonging to the botanical family of Amaryllidaceae. This uniquely cultivated ancient plant with edible bulbs is the third most

important horticultural crop after potato and tomato and is widely consumed throughout the world, mainly for its distinctive flavour (Teshika et al., 2019). Purple onions are important for both feeding and medicinal purposes. It has

been utilized for thousands of years for remedial purposes. It was recommended by medieval doctors to alleviate cough, headache, snake bite, hair loss and other ailments (Upadhyay, 2016). Oxidative stress is a state in which oxidation and oxidants exceed the antioxidant systems in the body, leading to imbalance between the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the level of antioxidants in the biological system (Yoshikawa and Naito, 2012). Biological free radicals are highly unstable and reactive molecules that have electrons available to react with various organ substrates such as DNA, proteins and lipids, causing damages to these biomolecules. Antioxidants are compounds that inhibit the oxidation of other compounds and prevent chemical damage caused by free radicals (Pandey and Rizvi, 2007). Sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium are important elements responsible for electrolyte balance, and their optimal concentration for proper biochemical and physiological activities of the cell is maintained by ion channels. These biologically important elements play a significant role in myriads of physiological functions. Sodium, the most abundant cation in the body, plays a significant role in fluid balance, osmotic regulation, and maintenance of membrane potential. Changes in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) can affect normal body sodium concentration. Sodium intake, under normal physiologic condition, matches sodium losses. Abnormally high sodium concentration (hypernatremia) presents with increased thirst, fatigue, restlessness, muscle irritability, and in severe conditions, cerebral cellular dehydration can occur, which can progress to hemorrhage, seizures, coma and death (Wang et al., 2017).

Haematological parameters, including red and white blood cell counts and haemoglobin concentration, are widely used clinical indicators of health and disease (Kelada *et al.*, 2012). Several studies have revealed that different medicinal plants could exert diverse effects on the haematological indices of animals (Albokhadaim, 2015) and humans (Fernandez, 2015). For instance, phenolic compounds and flavonoids contained in purple onions have numerous biological activities such that they can interact with reactive oxygen species and thus terminate the chain reaction before cell viability is seriously affected (Kumar and Pandey, 2013). The lack of specific information on the effects of purple onion extract on the weight, serum electrolytes, liver function parameters and haematological indices associated with oxidative stress induced by paracetamol in albino Wistar rats made it necessary to investigate these activities, and that constitute the aim of this study.

2.0 Material and Method

2.1 Study area

Extraction and animal studies were conducted in the Department of Biochemistry Laboratory, Faculty of science, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. While the analysis of electrolyte, liver function and haematological parameters were undertaken at Enis biomedical laboratory, Igbogene, Bayelsa State. Bayelsa State is located within latitude 4⁰/5/N and Latitude 5⁰/23 South in the Federal republic of Nigeria (Ikimi and Addy, 2024).

2.2 Plant sample collection and authentication

The purple onion (*Allium cepa*) samples were bought from a seller in Swali market in Yenagoa and authenticated/identified by a botanist in the Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

2.3 Plant sample extraction and processing

Seventy-five grams (75g) of the ground sample was soaked in 750ml of 70% water in ethanol and then placed in a water bath to evaporate, resulting in the yield of the extract. This was filtered using 3 layers of muslin cloth and then with Whatman paper (No.4). The filtrate was concentrated at 60°C using a water bath. The concentrated extract was reconstituted in normal saline ethanol at a concentration of 200mg/ml and stored at 4°C until further analysis.

2.4 Animal specimen and study population

Thirty healthy male Wistar albino rats weighing between 200g and 300g were used for this study. The animals were procured from the animal house of the University of Port Harcourt. The rats were kept in standard animal cages and acclimatized in the animal house, in the Department of Biochemistry, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State for 14 days and allowed free access to pelleted chicken feed and water. Mead's resource equation was utilized for the calculation of the sample size (Kirkwood and Robert, 2010). The equation is stated and the components defined. $E = N - B - T$, where: N is the total number of individuals or units in the study (minus 1). B is the blocking component, representing environmental effects allowed for in the design (minus 1). T is the treatment component, corresponding

to the number of treatment groups (including control group) being used, or the number of questions being asked (minus 1). E is the degrees of freedom of the error component, and should be somewhere between 10 and 20. The study constituted of six groups (T = 5), with 5 animals per group, making 30 animals in total (N = 29), without any further stratification (B = 0), then E would equal 24, indicating that the sample size is very suitable for the research.

2.5 Ethical clearance

Ethical clearance was obtained from the animal research ethics committee of the Department of Biochemistry, Faculty of Science, Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The Animal Welfare Act of 1985 of the United States of America for Research and Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (IACUC) protocols were stringently adhered to (Benjamin and Jean, 2016).

2.6 Selection criteria

Rats used were apparently healthy and active as confirmed and approved by a veterinary doctor. Rats showing signs and symptoms of illness were excluded from the research. Also excluded were rats with any form of derangements. Contaminated blood samples were rejected.

2.7 Induction of oxidative stress

Two grams (2g) of Acetaminophen (paracetamol) was dissolved in 20ml of dimethyl sulfoxide. Oxidative stress was induced by the oral administration of 2g/kg of the solution to the experimental subjects. After observing the experimental animals for 24hours, some

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were sacrificed and used to ascertain the presence of oxidative stress.

2.8 Experimental design

Completely randomized block design (CRBD) was used for this study. The animals were randomly grouped into six (6) groups, with five (5) animals in each group. Group 1 (normal control) was administered normal saline; group 2 (negative control) were induced with oxidative stress using paracetamol without treatment with the purple onion extract. Groups 3, 4 and 5 (treatment groups 1, 2 and 3) were treated with 125mg/kg, 250mg/kg and 500mg/kg of the extract respectively for 28 days, while group 6 (positive control) were administered 1ml of 100mg/dL of the extract. All groups were fed with pelleted chicken feed and distilled water *ad libitum*.

2.9 Collection and preparation of blood samples

Blood was collected via cardiac puncture into appropriate specimen bottles. Afterwards, the blood samples were centrifuged for 10mins at 2000 rpm and the supernatant was collected for electrolyte and liver function analysis. Whole blood was used for haematological analysis (Sule *et al.*, 2017; Ness, 1999).

2.10 Analysis of blood samples

The Mg, K and Ca content of the samples were determined using the method of Kabiru *et al.* (2016). Cl and Na content of the samples were determined using the method of Skeggs and Hochstrasser, (1964). Bicarbonate content of the samples were determined using the method of Roger *et al.* (1976). The liver function tests and albumin content of the samples were conducted

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using the method of Limdi and Hyde (2003). Total protein content of the samples was determined using Biuret method (Gonall *et al.*, 1949). Haematological parameters of the samples were determined according to the method of Cheesbrough, (2000).

2.11 Statistical analysis

Results were analyzed statistically using One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) under Turkey Kramer Multiple Comparison Test and Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20. Values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

4.0 Results and Discussion

Figure 1: Chart showing weights of the experimental animals at the initial and final weeks of the experiment

Figure 2: Chart showing effect of purple onion extract on ALT, AST and ALP activity of paracetamol-induced oxidative in Wistar rat. ALP: alkaline phosphatase; ALT: alanine aminotransferase; AST: aspartate aminotransferase

Figure 3: Chart showing effect of purple onion extract on the levels of albumin and total protein in paracetamol-induced oxidative stress in Wistar rat.

Figure 6: Chart showing the result of the effect of purple onion extract on the pack cell volume of paracetamol-induced oxidative stress in albino rats.

Figure 4: Chart showing the result of the effect of purple onion extract on the red blood cell of paracetamol-induced oxidative stress in Wistar rats.

Figure 5: Chart showing the result of the effect of purple onion extract on the haemoglobin count of paracetamol-induced oxidative stress in Wistar rats.

DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the effect of purple onion on the weight of the animals, indicating the varying weight changes between the initial and final weeks. The result shows that the negative control (untreated) group presented a much higher weight difference ($100 \pm 3.51\text{g}/160.25 \pm 19.85\text{g}$) when compared to treatment groups 1, 2 and 3 and the normal control groups ($83 \pm 1.80\text{g}/122 \pm 4.82\text{g}$), ($106.66 \pm 2.46\text{g}/151.33 \pm 7.28\text{g}$), ($94.66 \pm 3.61\text{g}/151.33 \pm 4.82\text{g}$) and ($91.75 \pm 5.67\text{g}/125 \pm 6.91\text{g}$) respectively, while the positive control group (treated with extract without induction) showed a decrease in weight ($75 \pm 7.07\text{g}/70 \pm 4.94\text{g}$). The expected weight gain may be attributed to normal growth and dietary factors in the absence of any experimental intervention. However, the untreated group serving as a reference for the impact of liver damage induced by paracetamol demonstrated a considerable increase in both mean initial and final weight compared to the group that was treated without induction of liver damage. The substantial weight gain may be an indication that there could be weight gain caused by fluid retention (Terblanche, 1991). The groups administered with varying doses of purple onion extract exhibited different patterns in weight changes. The treatment groups demonstrated modest variations, suggesting that higher dosage does not necessarily correspond to more significant weight changes (Nwonuma et al., 2021). The positive control group exhibited a

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notable decrease in both the mean initial and final weights. This substantial weight loss raises questions about the potential adverse effects or toxicity associated with this specific dosage (Riyaz et al., 2012).

Table 1 shows the serum electrolytes levels of the experimental animals with paracetamol induced oxidative stress and administered various doses of purple onion extract. From the results, there is a decrease in the mean concentration of the serum electrolytes in the normal control group when compared to all other groups except for Ca and bicarbonate. Statistical analysis shows that there is no significance difference ($p>0.05$) in the serum electrolytes between the groups except for Mg. It is observed that Mg presents a significant increase in concentration after treatment ($2.17\pm 0.14\text{mg/dL}$) when compared to the normal control group ($0.99\pm 0.29\text{mg/dL}$). This increase, however, decreases with an increase in the dose of the extract administered. Hence, an increased dose of the purple onion extract led to a decrease in the Mg concentration. The analysis of the K levels shows an increase in the K level in the negative control group which decreased with treatment by the extract. However, the normal control showed a lower concentration of 2.85mMol/L , which is less than 3.6mMol/L , thus indicating mild hypokalemia. The extract increased the Ca level in the treatment group 1 ($35.15\pm 20.03\text{mg/dL}$) which decreased with subsequent increases in doses of 250mg/kg ($13.80\pm 0.72\text{mg/dL}$) and 500mg/kg ($17.14\pm 4.26\text{mg/dL}$). When compared to the laboratory values for Ca ($8.5\text{-}10.2\text{mg/dL}$), the treatment and normal control groups presented hypercalcemia, which signals a Ca levels elevation impact of the extract. This finding corresponds with a study that reported an increase in bone density following administration of the extract (Matheson et al., 2009). The extract increased the Cl level in the treatment groups ($85.21\pm 6.83\text{mg/dL}$, $61.42\pm 1.33\text{mg/dL}$ and $84.58\pm 6.37\text{mg/dL}$) when compared to the normal group ($48.74\pm 7.72\text{mg/dL}$). This was also observed in Na, where treatment groups have higher values than the control groups except for the positive control group. These findings align with the report of related studies on the effects of medicinal plants on serum electrolytes (Çubukçu et al., 2019; Watanabe et al., 2018). Bicarbonate levels were not significantly different across the

groups. The result corresponds with the findings of Ghalehkandi et al., (2014). Albumin and total protein levels were significantly higher in treatment group 3 which received the highest dose of the extract. This corresponds with the findings of Dorrigiv et al., (2021).

The liver is subject to xenobiotic-induced injury because of its central role in the metabolism of xenobiotics. Increased serum levels of liver enzymes are clinical signs of hepatic injury resulting from loss of hepatocyte membrane integrity (Gu and Manautou, 2012). The result (figure 2) shows that the levels of serum liver enzyme - alkaline phosphatase, was significantly reduced when the negative control group is compared to the treatment groups. Treatment of animals with paracetamol is known to cause severe hepatic injury as evident in the elevated AST, ALT and ALP levels in the negative control. These increases indicate that paracetamol induces hepatocellular damage that alters the structure and function of liver cells (Kumar et al., 2013). The result of the red blood cell count (figure 4) show similarity among all treatment groups. Though all treatment groups fell within the normal range of red blood cells count which is 6.24 to 7.46 million cells per microliter (cells/mcL). There was a dose-dependent increase in red blood cells count among the treatment groups when compared with the negative control. An increase in the red blood cells count displays the blood-promoting action of the onion juice extract as previously reported by Griffiths et al., (2002) and AB, (2013). The result of the haemoglobin counts is shown in figure 5. The haemoglobin counts of the study groups were within close ranges except that of treatment group 3 (500mg/kg) which was significantly higher (13.3mg/dL). This result aligns with that of the study carried out by Samson *et al.* (2012). The result of pack cell volume is shown in figure 6. There was a dose-dependent increase in pack cell volume among the treatment groups when compared with the negative control. However, all treatment groups fell within the normal range of pack cell volume (40-50%). This result corresponds with the findings of Banerjee and Maulik (2002), Adebolu *et al.* (2011) and Ugwu and Omale, (2011).

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CONCLUSION

This study investigated the effect of purple onion (*Allium cepa*) extract on the weight, serum electrolytes, liver function parameters and haematological indices associated with oxidative stress induced by paracetamol in albino Wistar rats. Animals in all the study groups except for the positive control group gained weight. The extract was able to maintain electrolyte balance in the experimental subjects without reversing the oxidative stress. High dosage of the extract elevated albumin and total protein levels. Haematological indices, including red blood cell count, hemoglobin and packed cell volume showed no significant differences ($p>0.05$) between the groups. The extract demonstrated significant hepatoprotective effects. Hence, it is

recommended for consideration as a traditional medicine for the management of liver injuries due to oxidative stress. Although further studies are required to understand the mechanisms underlying the observed therapeutic effects and to provide guidelines on effective dosages and safety limits.

Table 1: Effect of purple onion extract on the serum electrolytes of experimental animals

Groups	Electrolytes					
	Mg (mg/dL)	K (mMol/L)	Ca ²⁺ (mg/dL)	Cl (mg/dL)	Na (mg/dL))	HCO ₃ (mMol/L)
NC	0.99±0.29	2.85±0.06	13.45±0.87	48.74±7.72	106.54±33.96	15.60±4.93
NeC	1.95±0.09	4.01±0.20	14.52±2.13	65.96±17.62	70.35±31.45	10.80±10.20
TG 1	2.17±0.14	3.23±0.10	35.15±20.03	85.21±6.83	113.80±7.74	15.00±8.19
TG 2	1.88±0.50	3.83±0.70	13.80±0.72	61.42±1.33	120.83±8.22	19.86±10.59
TG 3	1.51±0.10	3.66±1.12	17.14±4.26	84.58±6.37	116.90±44.91	16.26±8.13
PC	1.42±0.12	4.20±0.06	10.11±0.83	78.75±14.20	116.96±26.60	20.00±10.40

NC: Normal control; NeC: Negative control; PC: Positive control; TG: Treatment group

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